

Gaze patterns as a measure of situation awareness in take-over situations in automated driving

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Abstract

At level 3 automated driving, the driver is out of the loop of the driving task for extended periods during the drive. At system boundaries, the driver must reengage in the driving task and gain situation awareness to successfully take back vehicle control and handle the take-over situation. A lot of development effort is being put on detecting situation awareness with gaze patterns. In the present study, we analyzed eye-tracking data in take-over situations from 31 participants of a driving simulator study on the usage of a level 3 automated driving system. The aim was to identify gaze patterns in the take-over situation that are independent of the driving scenario. We found that gaze patterns in a take-over situation are heavily dependent on the driving scenario. In situations with an acoustic preannouncement, participants glanced at the forward road already before and also after the take-over request. We found that glances to the mirrors were evident only in situations that required a lane change and therefore the visual scanning of side and rear traffic. Only glances to the instrument cluster at the moment of the take-over request were evident for all scenarios. There were no relevant differences in gaze behavior between situations with driving errors and situations without errors. In conclusion, the results suggest that there is no universal glance strategy for building situation awareness in response to a take-over request. Glance pattern seem highly dependent on the requirements of the traffic scenario. Further situational information might be needed to evaluate situation awareness based on gaze behavior.

Keywords: Automated Driving, Situation awareness, Eye-tracking, Glance Patterns

1. Introduction

Automated Driving (AD) technology promises to make travelling more efficient, more convenient and safer; and to make mobility more accessible (NHTSA, 2020). The European project Hi-Drive (<https://www.hi-drive.eu/>) addresses still existing challenges for making AD a success both on a technical level but also with respect to potential users. One mayor challenge here is to design the AD and especially the user interface such that it allows to handle and use the system safely.

The automation of more and more parts of the driving task implicates a shift of the driver's attention from the road and driving-related cues to non-driving related tasks, thus taking the driver "out of the loop" of driving control. At the system's functional limits or at system errors however, the driver is required to get back into the loop to be able to take back vehicle control at short notice. In level 2 AD (L2-AD; SAE, 2021), where the driver is not in physical control, but monitors the driving task, they are considered "on the loop" (Merat et al., 2018). Being "in", "on" or "out of" the control loop are not discrete states but rather levels on a continuum. Studies show that the more drivers are out of the loop of driving control during AD, the longer it takes them to resume vehicle control in critical situations (Gold, Damböck, Lorenz, & Bengler, 2013; Louw et al., 2017). Research shows that characteristics of non-driving related tasks influence how "far" the driver is out of the loop. Drivers engaged with manual-visual task needed more time to resume control after a take-over request (TOR) than drivers engaged with a visual task (Naujoks, Purucker, Wiedemann, & Marberger, 2019).

Level 2 AD (L2-AD) systems that are currently on the market typically oblige the driver to keep their hands on the wheel or their eyes on the road, thus to remain “on the loop”. Higher level ADS however, i.e. SAE level 3 and higher, do not require the driver to stay on the loop. Still at boundaries of the function, the driver will be required to get back in the loop and take back control at system limits. When a TOR is issued at system limits, the driver needs to gain situation awareness when taking control. Depending on characteristics of the system and of the situation the driver might be required to react within a few seconds and take back vehicle control. During this transition process it is important that the driver gains a correct understanding of the driving situation and its challenges to be able to react appropriately and resume control safely. This situational understanding that is linked to a situationally adapted decision and reaction is discussed as situation awareness in the literature.

1.1. Situation awareness in driving with AD

Situation awareness was first investigated in aviation and is closely linked to the out-of-the-loop concept. Situation awareness is defined as “*the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and the projection of their status in the near future*” (Endsley, 1988, p. 97). Situation awareness involves perceiving relevant cues in the environment (level 1), understanding their meaning in relation to the person’s goals (level 2) and understanding what will happen in the future (level 3). If it comes to situation awareness with automation, (Endsley, 2018, p. 4) states three mechanisms by which situation awareness can be reduced:

1. “Poor vigilance when people become monitors, which is often coupled with increased trust or over-reliance on the automation,
2. Limited information on the behavior of the automation and/or the relevant system and environment information due to either intentional or unintentional design decisions, and
3. A reduced level of cognitive engagement that comes from becoming a passive processor rather than an active processor of information.”

Studies on situations awareness while driving with low levels of automation show that situation awareness is improved for drivers using an ACC when they are motivated to detect objects in the environment (De Winter, Happee, Martens, & Stanton, 2014) and when warned with a two-stage warning instead of a one-stage warning in take-over scenarios (Ma et al., 2021).

For AD systems that do not require the driver to remain in or on the loop of driving control, but do require them to get back into the driving task after a TOR, it can become necessary that the driver must gain situation awareness within a short time frame during the process of taking control back. Especially in critical situations, for example at sudden system limits, one challenge of AD design is to support the driver in gaining situation awareness in a takeover situation. Furthermore, there are approaches for user interfaces for AD that help keeping the driver in the loop during AD (e.g., Capallera et al., 2023; Yang, Karakaya, Dominiononi, Kawabe, & Bengler, 2018; You, Yan, Zhang, & Cui, 2022).

1.2. Measuring situation awareness

In the literature on situation awareness in driving as well as in other contexts e.g., aviation, interview or questionnaire methods like SAGAT (Endsley, 1995) or SART (Taylor, 2017) are used as well as eye tracking (Moore & Gugerty, 2010; van de Merwe, van Dijk, & Zon, 2012), physiological measures (T. Zhang et al., 2020) or probe measures. With probe measures, knowledge on the situation is asked from the user directly in or after the situation (Strybel et al., 2016). In AD studies, situation awareness is mainly investigated by means of eye

tracking measures, i.e. visual attention (Liang et al., 2021), by the response to critical events (Gold et al., 2013; Merat & Jamson, 2009) and also by probe measures (e.g., Sirkin, Martelaro, Johns, & Ju, 2017).

Numerous studies investigated the effect of driver states - like distraction or fatigue - on takeover reactions (for an overview of studies, see B. Zhang, de Winter, Varotto, Happee, & Martens, 2019). Although not addressing the question of situation awareness in takeover situations explicitly, it can be assumed that the investigated conditions at least partly impact the level of situation awareness prior to the TOR, i.e. the extent to which the driver is in vs. out of the loop or in the process of gaining situation awareness during the takeover reaction. In such studies, the focus is not on assessing situation awareness itself but the impact of degraded situation awareness on performance. In many takeover performance studies, researchers attempt to maintain controlled takeover situations while varying the driver state before the TOR (e.g., distracted, fatigued, or after sleep) or characteristics of the AD system, such as the user interface (Capallera et al., 2023), level of automation (Dillmann et al., 2021) or time budget during takeover (Pipkorn, Tivesten, & Dozza, 2022).

In studies on take-over performance, frequently used measures of attentional process are the occurrence and timing of on-road glances and glances to other relevant areas of interest (AOI) like the instrument cluster or the mirrors etc. (Dillmann et al., 2021; Pipkorn, Dozza, & Tivesten, 2022; Wörle, Metz, Othersen, & Baumann, 2020). These analyses imply that the visual scanning strategies are relevant for the takeover reaction. It is assumed that after being partly out of the loop prior to or while taking the control back, drivers collect information on the current driving situation as an important part of the takeover reaction. Therefore, awareness and understanding of the current driving situation is achieved mainly by visual perception and here an appropriate scanning strategy is crucial.

1.3. Visual perception and situation awareness

The proposed link between scanning strategies and situation awareness is also supported by research in aviation. Here, research on situation awareness established a close link between errors due to insufficient situation awareness and errors of attention allocation (McCarley, Wickens, Goh, & Horrey, 2002; Wickens et al., 2008). It could be shown that better situation awareness is related to a higher proportion of glances to task relevant areas of interest (Moore & Gugerty, 2010; van de Merwe et al., 2012).

Considering this research on visual scanning with regard to the concept of situation awareness, gaze measures allow an insight into the first level of situation awareness according to the model by Endsley – perception. The second level - comprehension of elements – is more difficult to assess as comprehension cannot be measured directly. Here, questionnaire, interview or probe measures can be applied (e.g., McKerral, Pammer, & Gauld, 2023; Sirkin et al., 2017). However, the consequences of the complete process of gaining situation awareness become evident in drivers' reactions and finally in the takeover performance. Behavioral errors are often interpreted as a consequence of insufficient situation awareness.

Research on scene perception states that humans are very efficient in perceiving the spatial structure and content of a natural scene (Castelhana & Krzyś, 2020). The basic content of a natural scene can be perceived in a fraction of a fixation (Anderson, Elder, Graf, & Adams, 2022) within 100 to 120ms, then objects that are central to the scene are fixated and processed. Therefore, the overall meaning of a scene guides eye movements and attentional processing (Rensink, 2000). Consequently, objects that are incongruent or at unusual places are perceived slower (Castelhana & Krzyś, 2020). Furthermore, in natural tasks like driving or making a sandwich, perception is directly linked to action (Engström, 2011; Hayhoe,

Shrivastava, Mruzek, & Pelz, 2003; Metz, 2009) in the sense that vision selects and guides action in a very close and not necessarily stage wise manner (Nakayama, Moher, & Song, 2023). For instance, for the task of making a sandwich, Hayhoe et al. (2003) could show that the initial fixations to a scene were comparably short and directed to task relevant as well as irrelevant objects. During the task, most fixations are directed at task relevant objects, directly guiding the next action. Here, it needs to be kept in mind that perception of a (driving) scene is not only based on foveal perception but relies on peripheral vision as well (Wolfe, Dobres, Rosenholtz, & Reimer, 2017).

Research on scene perception and vision / action interplay indicate a strong impact of situational characteristics and task demands on visual scanning. This is an aspect that has not been investigated so far in the context of takeover reactions in L2/L3-driving or in the context of situation awareness. Like described, in experimental studies it is mostly tried to keep the situation constant and to manipulate the drivers' state or system characteristics. Besides the perception of the forward driving scene, there are also other parts of information that might be relevant for gaining situation awareness but are not perceivable from the first on-road glance. This is because this information is located not in the forward view but elsewhere and therefore requires a shift of gaze e.g. to the mirrors or the vehicle's instrument cluster.

2. Research questions

With regard to takeover situations with L2 or L3-AD it is tried to develop measures or indicators that allow to draw conclusion on the level of situation awareness by the driver while being in AD mode (Capallera et al., 2023; Sirkin et al., 2017). The idea is that it might be possible to assess whether the current level of situation awareness is sufficient for a safe transition of control and in case not, either to prevent the driver from taking control back or to provide further support to improve situation awareness (Capallera et al., 2023).

Such a design concept requires that situation awareness can be assessed prior to the actual transition of control, this means between the TOR (or shortly before) and the deactivation of AD by the driver. During this stage, driving behavior cannot be used as an indicator since the vehicle is still in AD mode. Assuming that after being out of the loop, situation awareness is mainly gained via visual scanning, investigation of gaze behavior is one possible approach to evaluate the driver's situation awareness.

Before such strategies and HMI concepts can be developed, more knowledge about visual processing in takeover situations and its relation to situational characteristics is needed. It needs to be understood whether there are components of visual scanning during takeover reactions that occur always in a similar way as part of a basic takeover reaction and whether and how situational characteristics come into play. To be more specific, it can be investigated which areas of interest like on-road, instrument cluster, mirrors etc. are looked at during a takeover situation, when that happens and how situational affordances interact. Furthermore, for on-road glances, which probably represent one of the main areas of interest, it can be investigated if there are certain characteristics that change over time or with the characteristics of the driving situation. To be able to use gaze behavior during takeover situations as an indicator for situation awareness, the following research questions need to be investigated:

- Is there a scenario-independent gaze strategy in the take-over situation?
- Which areas of interest are relevant for that strategy?
- How is the gaze behavior impacted by situational characteristics?
- Is there a link between observed gaze behavior and takeover performance?

For this publication, data from a study on usage and acceptance of L3-AD is used and analyzed with focus on gaze behavior during takeover situations. The data is analyzed to gain first insights for the listed research questions and to derive recommendations for future studies.

3. Methods

3.1. Experimental design

The data used for the following analyses stems from a driving simulator experiment on the impact of repeated usage of an L3-AD on user acceptance, system handling and takeover performance (for a detailed description of the study, see Metz et al., 2021). The study was conducted in the high-fidelity moving base driving simulator of the WIVW GmbH. The simulation software was SILAB® Version 6.0 (WIVW GmbH, Veitshöchheim). The study focused on acceptance, evaluation and usage of L3-AD by ordinary, non-professional drivers. Participants used a simulated L3-AD motorway system during six test drives. The tested system implementation was based on the descriptions of L3-AD motorway systems to be tested in the on-road tests of L3Pilot (Griffin, Sauvaget, Geronimi, Bolovinou & Brouwer, 2020).

Drivers were invited to participate in a study on long-term effects of a motorway L3-AD. The study consisted of six driving sessions on six different days where the motorway AD system could be used. In all drives, the drivers were free to use the L3-AD as they liked, meaning they could activate and deactivate it and attend to NDRAs as they wished. Throughout the drives, the drivers experienced various takeover situations in which the AD required them to take control back with a time budget of 15 seconds. These takeover situations were chosen and designed with the aim to be realistic situations in which a L3 AD might not be able to handle the situation on its own.

As can be seen in Table 1, the takeover situations varied with regard to the reason of the TOR and what had to be done by the driver after taking control back to solve the situation safely. Furthermore, three of the six takeover scenarios had an acoustic and visual preannouncement through the navigation system which indicated the on-coming scenario already before the actual TOR.

Table 1: Overview of takeover scenarios.

Situation	Reason for TOR	Preannounc.	Required driver action
Exit 	The end of drive is reached. The motorway needs to be left at the next exit. The navigation system informs about the exit before the TOR.	Yes	Change the lane to the right to the exit lane. Exit the highway.
Intersection 1 	The motorway needs to be exited and the road followed in the direction shown at the navigation system and on traffic signs. The navigation system informs about the intersection before the TOR.	Yes	Change lane to the right to the exit lane. Follow the direction given in navigation system and by signs.

Intersection 2

The motorway needs to be exited and the road followed in the direction shown at the navigation system and on traffic signs. The navigation system informs about the intersection before the TOR.

Yes

Change lane to the right to the exit lane. Follow the direction given in navigation system and by signs.

Lane markings

The AD cannot follow the lane because of missing lane markings.

No

Follow the lane until the AD becomes available again.

Construction site

There is a construction site where lanes get narrower and bend to the left and with a speed limit of 80km/h.

No

Slow down, follow lane into the construction site.

Moving construct.

There is moving construction site on the driver's lane which is preannounced by a road sign. The lane is blocked and the construction site needs to be passed on another lane.

No

Change lanes to pass the moving construction site.

3.2. Data logging

During all drives, gaze behavior was logged with the three-camera system SmartEye Pro (SmartEye, Gothenburg). Furthermore, the logging included synchronized data from the driving simulator (e.g. status of AD, steering angle, gas pedal, vehicle data etc.). Drivers' reaction in the takeover situations was rated based on the video with the takeover controllability rating (TOC-rating, Naujoks, Wiedemann, Schömig, Jarosch, & Gold (2018)).

3.3. Sample

N=31 drivers participated in all six experimental drives. The type and number of takeover situations varied between the different drives (e.g. exit at the end of every drive, construction site 1 only once during all drives). As drivers were free to use the ADF as they liked, some of the potential takeover situations were driven manually because drivers deactivated the ADF sometime before the TOR. As a consequence, the number of situations for which gaze behavior can be analyzed varies between situations (see Table 2).

3.4. Analysis

The gaze behavior is analyzed for the different takeover situations. For this, the data is divided into segments of one second duration starting 10 seconds before the TOR and

ending 20 seconds after. For each segment and takeover situation, the following indicators are derived:

- Proportion of time the gaze is directed to relevant AOIs:
 - Windshield, i.e. forward road
 - Instrument cluster with information on vehicle and AD status
 - Mirrors, combining right, left and rear mirror
 - Interior display with information from navigation system
 - Undefined area including all other glances as well as loss of gaze tracking
- Mean and standard deviation of horizontal (heading) and vertical (pitch) gaze position for glances directed at the windshield

For the listed parameters it is investigated whether and when there is an impact of the situation on gaze behavior. Furthermore, it is tested whether there is a relation between takeover performance and gaze behavior. Takeover performance is assessed with the video-based TOC-rating, for more details see <https://toc-rating.de/en/>) which categorized the takeover reaction based on a standardized evaluation criteria into safe takeover reactions without error, takeover reactions with errors and safety critical takeover reactions. Table 2 shows the number of takeover situations rated to be without errors, with errors and with severe errors separately for the different situations. As already stated, the overall number of situational instances varies. Furthermore, it can be seen that there are more simple situations like the situation lane markings with a higher proportion of takeover reactions without errors and more difficult situations like intersections or the moving construction site with a higher proportion of takeover reactions with errors. Severe errors were observed in only one situation.

Table 2: Number of analysed takeover scenarios with different levels of takeover performance.

Situation	Takeover performance			Sum
	No errors	Errors	Severe errors	
Exit	23	148	0	171
Intersection 1	4	27	0	31
Intersection 2	2	28	1	31
Lane markings	66	46	0	112
Construction site	14	51	0	65
Moving construct.	9	19	0	28

For the analysis of situational impact, repeated measure ANOVAs are calculated over all time segments including the takeover situation as independent factor. In case of a significant interaction, separate one-way ANOVAs are calculated per time segment to explore at which timepoints situational impacts occur. There is no alpha correction because the analysis is an exploratory one which does not aim at proving a defined hypothesis.

To analyze whether gaze behavior differs between different levels of takeover performance, the situations exit, lane markings and construction site are analyzed. This is because in those situations, there is a certain variation in takeover performance (see Table 2) with takeover being partly solve without and partly with errors. Here, repeated measure ANOVAs are calculated over all time segments including the takeover performance as independent factor. This is done separately for the three situations.

4. Results

4.1. Impact of takeover scenarios on areas of interest

The first approach analyzes the impact of the takeover situation on the proportion of visual attention that is directed to the different AOIs for the time period 10 seconds prior to the TOR until 20 seconds after the TOR. This is calculated separately for the different AOIs including the takeover situation as independent factor. Figure 1 shows the proportion of time looked at the different AOIs split per takeover situation. There is a significant interaction between time and takeover situation for all analyzed AOIs (Instrument cluster: $F(159, 12510)=5.0$, $p<0.001$; interior display: $F(150, 12510)=1.3$, $p<0.01$; mirror: $F(150, 12510)=9.6$, $p<0.001$; undefined: $F(150, 12510)=14.3$, $p<0.001$; windshield: $F(150, 12510)=7.7$, $p<0.001$). Consequently, separate one-way ANOVAs are calculated to assess the impact of the takeover situation separately per time segment. Table 3 shows for which AOIs and time segments significant impact of the takeover situation can be found. For glances to the windshield, i.e. forward road there is a difference between situations with a hint preannouncing the upcoming TOR like the exit and the two highway intersections ($F(150, 12510)=7.7$, $p<0.001$) and those without. With a preannouncement, there is a higher proportion of on-road glances already in the period before the TOR. Furthermore, in those situations, there are also more glances to the instrument cluster ($F(150, 12510)=5.0$, $p<0.001$) in the period six to three seconds before the TOR and, accordingly less glances to undefined areas ($F(150, 12510)=14.3$, $p<0.001$).

Figure 1: Proportion of time the gaze is directed to the different analyse AOIs separate for the takeover scenarios. The analysis is done in time periods of one second starting 10 seconds before the TOR and ending 20 seconds after the TOR.

After the TOR, glances to the mirror are overall few. Glances to the mirror occur more frequently only in the situation “moving construction site” with a small peak around 6 seconds after the TOR and then again with maximum of about 20% of time at the end of the analyzed section 10 to 15 seconds after the TOR. In this situation, the increase is related to a lane change that is necessary to solve the situation safely. For the instrument cluster, there is a strong and sudden increase with a peak in second 1 after the TOR for all situations.

If a closer look is taken at the time directly after the TOR, in second 0, which is the first second directly after the TOR, there is a difference between the situations that is based on

the impact of the preannouncement for glances to the instrument cluster and to the windshield. Then, the situational impact disappears for three seconds, and reappears in second 4. Now, there are more glances to the instrument cluster in the situation with bad lane markings. This is a rather short situation and here drivers either expect the AD to become available again already four seconds after the TOR or they are not sure about the reason for the TOR and check the instrument cluster for more information on the AD status.

To remove the effect of pre-knowledge, in a second step only situations without preannouncement are compared (for results of separate one-way ANOVAs see Table 4). Now, the situational impact on the proportion of glances directed at the different AOIs starts with second 2 after the TOR. In the first two seconds after a TOR there is no difference between situations. Then, situational impacts can be observed mainly for the mirrors. From second 8 on, there is a significant situational impact on multiple AOIs (windshield, mirrors, instrument cluster; see Table 4).

4.2. Change of relevant AOIs over time

Taking the previous results into account, the analyzed time period is shortened to two seconds before until 5 seconds after the TOR and the takeover situations are grouped into with and without preannouncement. As can be seen, before the TOR there is a difference between the two situational groups with regard to on-road glances (sign. Interaction time x sit-group: $F(7, 5845)=29.1, p<0.001$) and glances to the instrument cluster (sign. Interaction time x sit-group: $F(7, 5845)=11.8, p<0.001$). Drivers use the preannouncement to direct more attention to areas providing driving relevant information like the windshield and the instrument cluster. As a consequence, less attention is directed to undefined areas (sign. Interaction time x sit-group: $F(7, 5845)=68.8, p<0.001$).

With the onset of the TOR, the amount of attention to the instrument cluster rises from 4% to 17% for situations without preannouncement. For situations with preannouncement, there is a similar increase of glances to the cluster to 18% directly after the TOR. For the group without preannouncement, the increase of attention to the road from 35% to 50% comes one second later which is followed by a further increase to around 60% after 4 seconds. With preannouncement the level of attention to the windshield is high already before the TOR and stays high with about 70% over the complete period with a slight drop to 64% around the time of the TOR which is caused by the increase of glances to the instrument cluster. For glances directed to the mirrors, there is overall a very low level of about 1% of time with a further decrease around the time of the TOR (second 0 and 1) to 0% (significant effect of time: $F(7, 5845)=3.7, p<0.001$). There is no effect of the preannouncement.

Figure 2: Average proportion of glances directed to the different AOIs for situations with (left) and without preannouncement for the time period 2 seconds before until 5 seconds after the TOR.

4.3. Analysis of on-road glances

To further investigate whether attentional strategies, e.g., allocation of attention to the road, are impacted by situational demands also in the early phase after the TOR, the variation and position of gaze is analyzed horizontally and vertically for the situations without preannouncement. Since this analysis only makes sense for glances to the windshield the analysis starts with second 0 because prior to the TOR there are frequently not enough on-road glances to calculate meaningful indicators. For the vertical orientation ($m(\text{Pitch})$) there is neither a significant effect of situation nor of time but a significant interaction ($F(10, 895)=4.4, p<0.001$). For the situation *lane marking* there is a change of orientation further downwards after four seconds, for the other situations there is no change of vertical orientation. Over the analyzed time period, there is a significant impact of situation on the horizontal orientation ($m(\text{Heading})$) of gaze: the gaze is oriented further to the right in the situation *construction site* compared to the two other situations ($F(2, 179)=15.6, p<0.001$). After the 1st second the gaze is directed more to the left in all situations ($F(5, 895)=4.7, p<0.001$). For vertical ($sd(\text{Pitch})$): $F(5, 840)=14.5, p<0.001$) and horizontal ($sd(\text{Heading})$): $F(5, 840)=13.6, p<0.001$) variation of gaze position, there is a significant decrease over time which is most pronounced from second 0 to second 1 for both directions. For the horizontal variation of gaze position there is also a significant interaction ($F(10, 840)=1.7, p<0.05$) and a significant effect of situation ($F(2, 168)=9.4, p<0.001$). The reduction of variation of gaze after second 0 can be found only for the situations “lane markings” and “construction site” but not for the moving construction site.

Figure 3: Impact of takeover situation on variation and position of on-road glance in the time segment from onset of TOR until 5 seconds after TOR.

4.4. Impact of takeover performance

As it could be shown that there is an impact of situational characteristics already early after the TOR, the relation between takeover performance and gaze related measures is analyzed per situation. In this analysis, three takeover situations are evaluated for which at least a certain variation in takeover performance can be observed (see Figure 4). For the situation "lane markings" there is an impact of TOC-rating on the proportion of time looked through the windshield ($F(1,138)=7.5$, $p<0.01$) and there is a significant interaction between time and takeover performance for glances directed at the instrument cluster ($F(5,690)=2.7$, $p<0.05$). Over the analyzed time period, in situations with a worse takeover performance (errors) there are more glances through the windshield compared to situations solved safely without errors. Furthermore, in situations with degraded performance there are more glances to the instrument cluster directly after the TOR but less in the following seconds. For the exit, there is a tendency for the effect of takeover performance on the proportion of glances directed through the windshield ($F(1,168)=2.9$, $p<0.09$). However, the effect is in the other direction compared to the situation lane markings: In situations with degraded performance there are less glances through the windshield compared to safe takeovers. For the situation construction site, there is no effect of takeover performance on the proportion of time looked at the different AOIs.

Figure 4: Impact of takeover performance on the proportion of glances directed to the windshield and the instrument cluster in the scenarios construction site, lane markings and exit.

For parameters assessing gaze behavior for on-road glances, there are only significant effects of takeover performance for the situation exit. Here, there is a higher horizontal ($F(1,147)=7.3, p<0.01$) and vertical variation ($F(1,147)=5.3, p<0.05$) of gaze position in situations solved with errors.

Figure 5: Impact of takeover performance on the variation of horizontal (heading) and vertical (pitch) gaze position in the situation exit.

5. Summary of results

Considering all implemented situations, there is a strong situational impact on measurable gaze behavior for all analyzed indicators before and after the TOR. To a large extent this is based on differences between situations with and without (acoustic) preannouncement by the navigation system. From a design perspective, this preannouncement can be seen as a TOR that occurs earlier in some situations than in others. The preannouncement results in a higher proportion of on-road and cluster glances in the time period prior to the actual TOR.

When only situations without a preannouncement are considered, there is no significant difference in the proportion of glances directed to different AOIs prior to the TOR and during

the first two seconds after the TOR. Then, situational differences come into play leading to situation specific differences in the proportion of glances directed to the mirrors. After eight seconds, the situational differences are highly pronounced with significant differences in all relevant AOs (windshield, mirror, instrument cluster).

Especially in situations without preannouncement, drivers were not attentive before the TOR which is reflected in a high proportion of glances to undefined areas. Directly after the TOR, there is an increase of glances directed at the instrument cluster and an increase of on-road glances for all situations. This shows that directly after the TOR drivers search for information from the driving environment and for information displayed on the instrument cluster. This information need seems to be independent of the driving situation. Already after two seconds, the driving situation highly impacts the visual search behavior. From then on, the appropriateness of gaze behavior can only be evaluated when situational characteristics are considered.

It is worth mentioning that glances to the mirrors – which sometimes are discussed as an indicator for safe take over reactions - occur more frequently in the only situation requiring a lane change, with a first peak around two seconds after the TOR and a second more pronounced peak starting after eight seconds. Situations with a lane change to the right (e.g. exit) are not related to a higher proportion of mirror glances.

A closer analysis of on-road glances shows vertically and horizontally a higher variation of gaze position during the first second after the TOR. This is independent of the takeover situation. Then, there is a decrease of variation that varies between situations. This indicates that directly after the TOR, there is a wide variation of gaze position indicating a more pronounced scanning of the scenery. The horizontal orientation of gazes differentiates between situations already in the first second after the TOR. This is in-line with research on the perception of natural scenes which indicates that the overall meaning of a scene is perceived within 100-120ms and then guides eye movements and attentional processing (Rensink, 2000). Also, for other tasks, a more pronounced visual scanning has been observed during first contact with a scene (Hayhoe, Shrivastava, Mruzek, & Pelz, 2003).

Results on the relation between takeover performance and gaze behavior are scarce and not very conclusive. In one situation, takeover reactions with errors are related to more, in another to less glances to the windshield. In only one out of three situations, variation of on-road glance position varies with takeover performance. Here, errors are related to a more pronounced visual scanning.

6. Discussion and Conclusion

Right after the onset of the TOR, there is already a situational impact on the horizontal alignment of gaze. This is in-line with results on scene perception which shows that the basic layout of a scene is perceived within milliseconds. However, the variation of gaze directed to the front scene is not impacted by situational characteristics during the first two seconds during which also a higher variation, that is a more pronounced visual scanning can be observed.

Results on the impact of situational characteristics show that already two seconds after a TOR, situationally adapted scanning behavior can be found. This implies that then, a basic situation awareness has already been developed and guides drivers' visual strategy and – not analyzed here – potentially also other components of the takeover behavior. Before that, there is an increase of glances to the instrument cluster that occurs in the first two seconds after the TOR. This increased search for information depicted on the instrument cluster can either be due to informational needs on the current vehicle state (like speed) or due to informational needs on the state of the AD. These two options cannot be differentiated in the

available data because both types of information were presented close to each other on the instrument cluster. Further research is required to better understand the informational needs with regard to vehicle and system status.

Later, there is strong situational impact on the proportion of time the different AOIs are looked at. Here, the low proportion of gaze directed to the mirrors is of special interest. In the literature, mirror glances are sometimes treated as an important component in the process of gaining situation awareness as they are the only option to perceive the rearward traffic scene. Results indicate that glancing at the mirrors is not a crucial component of a general strategy of gaining situation awareness. Instead, it seems that mirror glances only occur in situations where the rear traffic is of special, action guiding interest, for instance because drivers prepare to change lanes. Again, based on the data it cannot be decided whether certain situational characteristics are the cause of the mirror glances or whether they are directly related to planning and execution of a lane change. In other words, mirror glances might occur to directly guide an action or they might reflect informational needs that are specific for that situation but not necessarily linked to action. Again, further research is needed to better understand the contribution of mirror glances to a takeover reaction as such compared to mirror glances as imminent part of conducting a lane change.

Gaze measures – as used in the present study – allow to gain insights in the first level of situation awareness: visual perception. The second and third level – comprehension and action – was derived from the takeover performance. However, we did not find any consistent relation between gaze behavior and the success of the takeover. This again confirms the observation that there is no general gaze behavior that is indicative of situation awareness and therefore for good performance. Findings from fundamental research on visual perception indicate that relevant cues in a scene are processed within a fraction of a second (Anderson et al., 2022). Glance durations to specific AOIs might therefore not be an adequate measure of understanding a scene and therefore, situation awareness.

The necessary glances after the TOR also depend on the state of knowledge before the TOR. In situations where drivers received information on the upcoming situation already before the TOR, the glance strategy was different. The same might apply to situations where the driver generally glances more at relevant areas. In another analysis of the same dataset, it was found that during the first drive with the system, drivers glanced more at the forward road than in following drives (Metz et al., 2021). This could be an indicator that drivers tried to maintain a higher level of situation awareness in the beginning to be able to take over control and after gaining trust in the system, they allow themselves to have lower situation awareness.

The relation between takeover performance and gaze behavior is a point that requires further research as it was quite challenging to be investigated with the available data. As shown, it is difficult to implement takeover scenarios such that they lead to takeover reactions with sufficient variation in takeover performance to allow that type of analysis. Due to the high impact of situational characteristics on gaze behavior conclusions on the relation between gaze and performance cannot be based on multiple situations but need to be drawn in a first step per situation.

It needs to be considered that the study was conducted in a motorway environment where most relevant information is on the forward road. Therefore, not much variance in gazes to other directions are required to get the relevant information. This might be one explanation for the low variance in gazes to other AOIs. In a more complex scenario, like for example in urban traffic, gazes to other directions like the side windows or the rear mirror might be more relevant to detect pedestrians, cyclists or more complex infrastructures. Therefore, a takeover situation in such a scenario would require glances to different AOIs and possibly

also a higher glance dispersion. However, it would still be difficult to define the “correct” gaze strategy to infer information on situation awareness. From a design perspective, the results implicate that it will be very challenging to judge the appropriateness or level of situation awareness based on gaze behavior. Environmental information might be needed to evaluate the appropriateness of gaze behavior.

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Table 3: Results of separate one-way ANOVAs. The Xs mark significant differences between takeover situations per analysed AOI and time segment. All takeover situations are included.

	Before TOR									After TOR																			
	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
WS	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Mirror								x			x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Cluster	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x			x	x	x		x				x			x	x	x	x	x
Display										x	x		x			x	x						x			x			
Undefined	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x							x	x	x	x	x	x

Table 4: Results of separate one-way ANOVAs. The Xs mark significant differences between takeover situations per analysed AOI and time segment. Only takeover situations without preannouncement are included.

	Before TOR									After TOR																			
	9	8	7	6	5	4	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19
WS												x						x	x	x	x		x	x	x				
Mirror								x				x	x		x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Cluster								x						x				x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Display																													
Undefined												x	x								x								

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